

A study on structural anisotropy and surface hydroxylation of nanorod units of triphasemesoporous TiO₂ for its application in photocatalytic degradation of organic pollutants in wastewater

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Abstract:

The paper focuses on studying the morphological development of brookite-dominated triphasemesoporous TiO₂ concerning crystallographic coherence. Brookite-enriched mesoporous TiO₂ nanoparticles were synthesised. The prepared material was proven to be a better photocatalyst than single-phase anatase titania and, at the market, existing P25 TiO₂. The major thrust was given to study the structural anisotropy of the prepared sample based on lattice defects of crystallographic planes, oriented attachment of nanocrystals, solution chemistry and surface hydroxylation phenomenon. The properties of morphology, characteristics of surface properties, and mechanisms of the nucleation and process of growth of the produced TiO₂ nanoparticles are all strongly influenced by the synthesis pH, according to observation. Structural anisotropy of the prepared titania was observed to be enhanced with an increment of synthesis pH. Planar defects in crystallographic planes were seen to be more prominent in the brookite-enriched mixed-phase TiO₂ with an increment of pH (namely at pH 5.5). These properties make the synthesised brookite-enriched mixed-phase TiO₂ an efficient photocatalyst (efficiency > 99.5% in 80 minutes) for phenol decomposition. The prepared photocatalyst will be very useful for degrading organic pollutants in wastewater to protect the environment.

Keywords: Triphase TiO₂, synthesis pH, structural anisotropy, oriented attachment, surface hydroxylation, photocatalysis, and phenol degradation.

1. Introduction

Photocatalysts have recently attracted much attention as scientists look for a long-term remedy for cleaning up pollutants from the air and water that are being polluted daily due to rising urbanisation and industrialisation (Seal et al., 2022; Yahya et al., 2018). Researchers have recently created a metal oxide as a photocatalyst which removes organic contaminants from aquatic bodies that are very effective and environmentally friendly (Lim et al., 2016; Gaya, 2014). Because of their outstanding performance, durability in underwater media, not harmful, suitable band structures for quick and efficient degradation of pollutants, and simple manufacturing procedures, undoped or doped TiO₂ nanostructures stand out among the others (Kumar et al., 2014; Hanaor et al., 2011). TiO₂ nanomaterials' photocatalytic effectiveness appears to be strongly influenced by the structure of the crystal, the process of morphology, defects in the lattice, mechanism of the phase composition, size of the particle, main characteristics of surface (area, mainly pore size and volume, one more thing that one is a surface-to-volume ratio), and contaminants of the chemical (Gaya, 2014; Kumar et al., 2014; Vorkapic et al., 1999; Barringer et al., 1985). At the moment, scientists are focusing on the synthesis of mixed-phase TiO₂ photocatalysts. In the current study, a brookite-enriched mixed-

phase TiO₂ photocatalyst was synthesised using a TiCl₃ precursor. In the recent study, the pH of the reaction solution was changed from 1.0 to 5.5 to produce mixed-phase TiO₂ enriched in brookite. In this study, an effort we have made to look into the physical cause of the morphology of synthetic mixed-phase TiO₂ systems dominated by brookite under various reaction circumstances. The primary focus of the current work was on understanding how the photocatalytic efficiency of brookite-enriched TiO₂ nanoparticles was influenced by crystal development, lattice defects, anisotropic features, and crystallographic coherence characteristic.

Using generated TiO₂ nanostructures under UV-C irradiation, a model organic pollutant (in this case, phenol) was photo-catalytically decomposed, and the process was comprehensively examined. Additionally, research on the chemical kinetics of phenol breakdown was carried out. Here, the photocatalytic actions of synthetic brookite-dominated and the mixed-phase prepared TiO₂ (produced in various pH ranging from 1.0 to 5.5), synthetic single-phase anatase TiO₂, and commercial TiO₂ - P25 [by Sigma-Aldrich] were compared. Compared to single-phase anatase and P25, brookite-dominated mixed-phase TiO₂ [produced at pH 5.5] exhibits greater catalytic effectiveness, according to this study.

2. Experimental

2.1. Material Synthesis

By solvothermal alcoholises of titanium trichloride in the presence of 100% ethanol and sodium hydroxide, brookite-enriched and the mixed-phase prepared TiO₂ Nano flower (we named it NRT) and the type microsphere (we called it MST) morphologies created. According to the variations in the molar concentrations of the chemicals utilised, pH values of the various solution were adjusted, for pH 1.0, named NRT-1.0, for 2.5, named NRT-2.5, 4.0, named NRT-4.0, and 5.5, designated as MST-5.5 respectively. To create various TiO₂ nanoparticle morphologies, varying molar ratios of TiCl₃ and NaOH to C₂H₅OH were used (i.e. NRT and MST samples). Atmospheric pressure and temperature were used for the entire process. The produced solution was moved to a Teflon liner and then heated to 150 °C for 18 hours in an autoclave. At the last of the solvothermal reaction that happened inside the autoclave, a solid white precipitate was formed. To get rid of the outside ions like Na⁺ and Cl⁻, the outcome precipitate product was washed numerous times in the mix-solution ethanol and distilled water. The material was then and keep it for calcination for two hours at 400 °C. The flow diagram for material synthesis given in Fig. 1.

Fig.1. Process flow diagram for material synthesis.

2.2. Material Characterisation

All of the synthesised samples in the current study were characterised using various well-established techniques. To know about the phase using XRD, and to get information about the size, and shape of samples, we did HRSEM, and many different techniques like EDS, and HRTEM, to know chemical composition, we did XPS, also Raman spectroscopy, UV-Vis absorbance spectroscopy, UV-Vis Diffusion Reflectance spectroscopy, and we did photoluminescence spectroscopy, to understand their morphologies, various physio-chemical properties, and photo-catalytic properties.

2.3. Study on adsorption phenomena and photocatalytic activity

All NRT and MST samples' photo-catalytic effectiveness and adsorption-desorption phenomenon were studied. In the model pollutant which we have taken in our laboratory is a phenol solution of optimisation concentration of 50 mg/L; the produced TiO₂ photocatalyst was introduced as an aqueous suspension with a catalyst loading of 1.0 gm/L. At room temperature and air pressure, the solution was stirred at 350 rpm using a magnetic stirrer and exposed to UV-C radiation. The experiments were carried out inside a quartz-jacketed 300 ml photo reactor. A UV-Visible Spectrophotometer was used to calculate the time-wise vanishing of phenol (identified at a wavelength of 270 nanometres) for a duration of each cycle of 80 minutes. After passing through a Millipore filter with a pore size of 0.45 microns, the catalyst-suspended phenol solution was examined after 15 minutes to track the rate at which the concentration of phenol degraded.

Following a photocatalytic degradation reaction, the level of TOC mineralisation in the phenolic solution, which is irradiated by UV light, was also determined by a TOC analyser. Chromatography analysis was done to separate the TiO₂ particles; before that, degraded

phenol solution in the photo-reactor was passed through a Millipore syringe filter with a pore size of 0.2 microns. High-performance liquid chromatography-mass spectrometry (HPLC-MS) in negative ion (ESI) mode was used to identify the intermediate by-products.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1. Phase and morphological study

3.1.1. XRD analysis

Through X-ray Diffraction analysis, the presence of different phases of the differently prepared samples was noticed and is depicted in Fig. 2.

Fig.2.1. XRD patterns of NRT-1.0 and NRT-2.5 sample.

Fig.2.2. XRD patterns of NRT-4.0 and MST-5.5 sample.

When dealing with MST samples, high crystallinity is anticipated. Furthermore, in all NRT samples as well as in the MST-5.5 sample, crystalline planes (121), (202), (221), (302), and (312) associated with the brookite phase were seen. The morphology and effectiveness of the photocatalytic reaction may be significantly influenced by the pH of the synthesis and the average crystal size.

3.2.2. S.E.M. analysis, E.D.S. analysis and T.E.M. characterisation

A detailed investigation was made through HRSEM and EDS showed in Fig. 3 and HRTEM Fig. 4 analyses of the synthesised samples. In the TiO₂ nanoparticles, HR-SEM pictures for NRT-1.0 and NRT-2.5 samples were investigated. Sharp rods consisting of hierarchical nanoflowers existed in low-level synthesis pH (~1.0 and 2.5) circumstances. In the MST-5.5 sample, spherical microspheres were present in hierarchical form. In the EDS experiment, different chemicals like Titanium, Oxygen and Carbon composition percentage were measured. In line with the HR-SEM images, the HR-TEM images also confirm the formation of nanoflower and the synthesised NRT samples [NRT-1.0, 2.5, 4.0 respectively] and another MST-5.5 prepared sample, respectively, have different microsphere morphologies. The samples are made up of smaller units of nanorods, although the MST-5.5 and NRT samples' nanorod units are other. In the produced nanoparticles, we examine the structural anisotropy in which the crystallographic alignment process arises in a specific direction of the crystallographic axis. One can determine whether crystallographic coherence is present in a sample.

Fig.3. Upper portion of the window shows HRSEM images of differently prepared TiO₂ samples and the lower portion shows EDS images of differently prepared TiO₂ samples.

Fig.4. HRTEM images of different prepared materials at different scales.

3.2.3. XPS analysis

The effect of surface OH⁻ and O²⁻ on the photocatalytic effectiveness of the prepared NRT and MST materials was examined using XPS analysis.

Fig.5. XPS image of prepared materials (Chemically present composition of all differently prepared samples.

In the synthetic TiO₂ samples, different fractional atomic masses present with Titanium 19.27%, Carbon 32.88%, and Oxygen 45.85% for the sample MST-5.5 and Titanium 11.48%, Carbon 43.19%, and Oxygen 45.33% for the NRT-4.5 sample, according to the XPS survey spectra are shown in Fig. 5. Peak intensities in XPS spectra represent the amount of material present at the surface, whereas peak positions represent its chemical and elemental makeup.

3.2.4. UV-Vis absorbance and UV-Vis DR spectroscopy By calculating the UV absorption capacity and band gap energy of the produced nanoparticles, the photocatalytic activity of the obtained TiO₂ nanoparticles was evaluated. Figure 6 shows the UV-Vis absorbance.

Fig. 6. show UV-VIS absorption spectra of synthesised samples (A1: c_t/c_0 vs time (removal of phenol time-wise) and (A: rate constant evaluation).

By graphing incident photon energy ($h\nu$) vs. $[F(R)h\nu]^{1/2}$ (Morales et al., 2019), the Kubelka-Munk function was used to calculate the band gap energy. Although MST-5.5 has a lower UV absorption capacity than NRT samples, there was little difference in the band gap energies (E_g) for different synthesised samples such as MST and NRT ($E_{g\text{MST-5.5}} = 3.06$ eV, $E_{g\text{NRT-4.0}} = 2.92$ eV, and $E_{g\text{NRT-2.5}} = 2.88$ eV).

3.3. Photocatalytic activity and kinetic study

By comparing the photocatalytic effectiveness of those NRT and MST-5.5 materials, the impact of the morphology of produced TiO₂ nanoparticles was examined depending on photocatalytic response. Experimental testing was done on the photocatalytic performance of synthetic triphase with brookite enriched TiO₂ (different NRT samples and MST-5.5 here), commercially available P25 and single-phase anatase (identified as SA here). As shown in Fig. 7, under similar conditions and a comparison was made.

Fig .7. Kinetics of degradation of phenol using six different types of samples (B: removal of phenol with different samples percentage-wise, B1: shows a comparison between reaction- rate-constant of different samples).

To assess the effectiveness of the degradation process and the kinetics of the reaction under UV-C irradiation, the time-wise disappearance of phenol concentration was determined. While different samples show different degradation efficiencies, for example, 78.20% in the case of NRT-1, NRT-2.5 shows 92.78%, NRT-4.0 shows 98.00%, SA shows 54%, and P25 displays about 23.49%, respectively, in 80 minutes, MST-5.5 exhibits high percentages of phenol degradation or 99.99%. The surface properties, light absorption capacity, crystalline structure, and phase distribution of the manufactured TiO₂ samples were also briefly examined to evaluate the variations in photocatalytic efficiency among them, as stated in the preceding sections.

3.4 Conclusion

With an aim to obtain an efficient photocatalyst for phenol degradation, four different brookite-dominated triphasemesoporous TiO₂ photocatalyst samples were synthesised by varying synthesis pH of the reaction solution. Up to nine rounds of phenol removal testing were conducted on the prepared brookite-enriched titania's catalytic activity. In 80-minute intervals, each cycle demonstrates a 99.5% elimination of the model contaminant phenol. The synthesised photocatalyst was proven to be far superior to single-phase anatase and commercially available P25 TiO₂. The MST-5.5 sample underwent a repeatability test to confirm its photostability for phenol degradation. Results show around 99.5% removal of phenol in 80 minutes in each and every cycle. One may conclude from the present work that mesoporous and microsphere morphology of triphase TiO₂ nanoparticles (brookite dominated) may be helpful in the degradation of phenol by MST-5.5. Additionally, by modifying the synthesis pH, orientated attachment, lattice defect, and surface hydroxylation, the produced triphase TiO₂ nanoparticles' catalytic efficiency could be altered. The findings of this study could be extremely helpful in developing wastewater treatment technology for the degradation of organic contaminants. This brookite-dominated TiO₂ nanomaterial can also be utilised for electrochemical analysis, water splitting, solar cell material, and hydrogen evolution, among other things.

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